

S2. Observable anchors

Purpose:

Observable indicators and typical traces per criterion to support consistent scoring and reduce halo effects.

Criterion	Observable indicators (examples)	Typical artifacts/traces	Boundary note (what it is / is not)
C1 Intention clarity	Purpose referenced in recurring decisions; teams can state purpose consistently	Strategy one-pager; decision memos referencing purpose	Not slogans only; must shape decisions
C2 Vision–frontline dialogue	Weak signals captured and discussed; decisions adjusted after frontline feedback	Feedback loop ritual minutes; issue log with actions	Not “surveys only”; must change choices
C3 Long-term orientation	Trade-offs include long-term impacts; investment decisions not purely short-term	Roadmap; risk/impact assessment notes	Not long-term talk; evidence in trade-offs
C4 Work practice mastery	Work steps understood (why/how); variation reduced through learning, not coercion	Standard work in use; coaching/training logs	Not obedience; mastery implies understanding
C5 Process understanding	End-to-end flow discussed; local optimizations identified and corrected	Process map; cross-functional flow review	Not isolated procedures; requires end-to-end system view
C6 Error management	Root-cause routines exist; lessons lead to preventive changes	RCA reports; updated standards/training after incidents	Not fast fixes only; learning must be visible
C7 Knowledge transfer	Onboarding consistent; knowledge survives departures	Onboarding plan; knowledge base/wiki updates	Not heroic mentoring only; must be repeatable
C8 Collective learning	Regular retrospectives; improvements tracked to closure and adopted	Kaizen log; after-action review notes	Not meetings without change; must alter practice
C9 Meaning at work (sense-making)	People can link tasks to shared aims; trade-offs explained as “why”	Team briefings; narrative of contribution in rituals	Not “happiness”; meaning = contribution clarity
C10 Quality of human relations	Respectful interaction norms; issues raised without personal attacks	Team working agreements; pulse/risk logs	Not “nice culture”; includes structured respect
C11 Cross-role cooperation	Joint problem-solving across roles; interface issues managed explicitly	Cross-functional review minutes; RACI used in practice	Not sequential handoffs only; needs interaction
C12 Recognition of work/craftsmanship	Feedback is fair and regular; expertise/effort is acknowledged	Recognition routines; performance feedback records	Not generic praise; must be credible and fair
C13 Accountability and steering	Decision rights clear; priorities/trade-offs explicitly steered	Governance charter; steering meeting records	Not blame; accountability = ownership of choices
C14 Human–system interaction	Users understand system effects; system rules are questioned/adjusted when needed	System training; change requests; model/rule documentation; configuration log	Not tool usage only; includes influence/orientation
C15 System adaptability/resilience	Standards evolve without chaos; changes tested and stabilized	Change management records; versioning of standards	Not constant change; resilience = controlled evolution